

**Novel Analytical Methods for Flame Retardants and Plasticizers based
on Gas Chromatography, Comprehensive Two-Dimensional Gas
Chromatography and Direct Probe Coupled to Atmospheric Pressure
Chemical Ionization-High Resolution Time-of-Flight-Mass Spectrometry**

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1 **Abstract**

2 In this study, we assess the applicability of different analytical techniques, namely direct probe
3 (DP), gas chromatography (GC) and comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography
4 (GCxGC) coupled to atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) with a high resolution
5 (HR)-time-of-flight (TOF)-mass spectrometry (MS) for the analysis of flame retardants and
6 plasticizers in electronic waste and car interiors. APCI-HRTOFMS is a combination scarcely
7 exploited yet with GC or with a direct probe for screening purposes and to the best of our
8 knowledge, never with GCxGC to provide comprehensive information. Due to the increasing
9 number of flame retardants and questions about their environmental fate, there is a need for the
10 development of wider target and untargeted screening techniques to assess human exposure to
11 these compounds. With the use of the APCI source, we took the advantage of using a soft
12 ionization technique that provides mainly molecular ions, in addition to the accuracy of HRMS
13 for identification. The direct probe provided a very easy and inexpensive method for the
14 identification of flame retardants without any sample preparation. This technique seems
15 extremely useful for the screening of solid materials such as electrical devices, electronics and
16 other waste. GC-APCI-HRTOF-MS appeared to be more sensitive compared to liquid
17 chromatography (LC)-APCI/atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI)-HRTOF-MS for a
18 wider range of flame retardants with absolute detection limits in the range of 0.5-25 pg. A variety
19 of tri- to decabromodiphenyl ethers, phosphorus flame retardants and new flame retardants were
20 found in the samples at levels from $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ to mg g^{-1} levels.

21 **KEYWORDS:** Direct probe, atmospheric pressure chemical ionization, comprehensive two-
22 dimensional gas chromatography, flame retardants, electronic waste

23 INTRODUCTION

24 Halogenated flame retardants (FRs) [e.g. polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) and
25 tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA)] are widespread in the environment due to their use in a variety
26 of electronics, clothes and furniture for enhancing fire safety. Due to their persistence,
27 bioaccumulative and toxic properties [1,2] authorities have restricted the use of PBDEs. The
28 European Union (EU) banned pentaBDE and octaBDE mixtures in 2004 [3] and decaBDE in
29 electric and electronic products in 2009 [4], with limits of 0.1 % by mass being set for pentaBDE
30 and octaBDE in products placed on the market. As a result of these regulations, the use of
31 alternative flame retardants is increasing. Decabromodiphenyl ethane (DBDPE) is used as a
32 substituent of decaBDE and the use of phosphorus flame retardants (PFRs), which are sometimes
33 also used as plasticizers, is increasing. New flame retardants have been reported for the first time
34 in the environment and in consumer products, such as tetrabromobisphenol-A-bis-(2, 3-
35 dibromopropylether) (TBBPA-BDBPE) in dust [5] and sediments [6] or U-OPFR [2, 2-bis
36 (chloromethyl) propane-1, 3-diyl tetrakis (1-chloropropane-2-yl) bis-(phosphate)] in baby
37 products [7]. Due to the lack of data on the identity and levels of flame retardants currently in
38 use, the development of proper, broad screening techniques for these compounds and possible
39 unknowns is highly desirable. In addition, a fast screening technique for flame retardants in
40 waste is needed.

41 Gas chromatography/electron capture negative ionization quadrupole MS (GC/ECNI qMS),
42 GC/high resolution mass spectrometry (GC/HRMS) and GC ion trap MS (GC/ITMS) have been
43 the most commonly used MS techniques for the determination of polybrominated diphenyl ethers
44 (PBDEs) [8]. Recent articles have shown the suitability of liquid chromatography (LC)-
45 atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) or LC-atmospheric pressure photoionization

46 (APPI) low resolution MS in the negative mode for the analysis of brominated flame retardants,
47 with $[M-Br+O]^-$ as the main ion due to in-source displacement reactions [9-11]. Owing to its
48 sensitivity in full-scan acquisition mode and high mass accuracy, HR full spectrum acquisition
49 techniques, such as HR-time-of-flight (TOF)-MS, have been increasingly used in the last decade
50 for both targeted and untargeted analysis [12]. The combination of a soft ionization technique
51 that generates spectral data rich in molecular ions with HRMS is especially suitable for
52 compound identification. In this study, APCI is assessed as ionization source for the analysis of
53 flame retardants coupled with a HR-TOF detector and for the first time in combination with
54 direct probe, GC or comprehensive two-dimensional GC (GCxGC). LC-electrospray
55 (ESI)/APCI/APPI-HRTOFMS methods were optimised and discussed for comparison with GC-
56 based methods.

57 Fast direct-probe or ambient ionization MS techniques without the need of chromatographic
58 separation and even sample treatment have arisen recently for the direct analysis of solid
59 materials [13] as a good alternative to matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization (MALDI). In
60 desorption electrospray ionization (DESI), which was introduced in 2004 [14, 15], a sample
61 surface is ionized by directing charged droplets produced from a pneumatically-assisted
62 electrospray and generates a mass spectrum that is similar to ESI. The so-called atmospheric
63 pressure solids analysis probe (ASAP), first reported in 2005 [16,17] operates on the same basis
64 as the APCI-direct probe, being both assemblies quite similar. In both APCI-ASAP and APCI-
65 direct injection probe the sample ionization takes place under heating for gas phase generation
66 and with a corona discharge that initiates an ion/molecule reaction. Applications have been made
67 mainly in the bio-analytical fields (reviewed in [18]) and polymer material [19-20] and more
68 recently in the food [21, 22] and environmental area [23-24]. A recent article exploits also the

69 combination of ASAP with a HR Orbitrap for polymer additives, reporting the detection of one
70 flame retardant [25]. The use of direct probe APCI-HRTOF-MS is here studied for the first time
71 for the fast screening of a wide variety of flame retardants and plasticizers without any sample
72 preparation.

73 APCI interfaces for use in combination with GC are recently commercially and are quite
74 promising for the analysis of non-polar volatile compounds, such as flame retardants, due the
75 higher resolution and less matrix ionization effects when compared to LC. First home-made
76 couplings were reported decades ago and more recently in 2005 [26-28]. GC-APCI couplings
77 have been scarcely exploited yet for real sample analysis and only some applications have been
78 reported, namely for the determination of pesticides using a GC-APCI-q-TOF-MS [29] or a triple
79 quadrupole analyzer (QqQ)-MS [30,31] as good alternatives to common electron ionization (EI)
80 sources, in which abundant fragmentation occurs.

81 The coupling of GCxGC with APCI-HRTOF-MS would provide with a comprehensive
82 information for screening. A number of articles have suggested the applicability of GCxGC with
83 low or medium resolution EI-TOF-MS (5000-7000 FWHM) [32-34] for screening of organic
84 contaminants, but to the best of our knowledge this is the first time that GCxGC is coupled to a
85 HRMS (>15000 FWHM) using a soft ionization source. GCxGC has been applied to the analysis
86 of PBDEs with EI-TOF low resolution MS using a combination of a non-polar and medium-
87 polar columns, the second dimension being mostly high temperature 8% phenyl-polycarborane-
88 siloxane [35], 50% phenyl-polysilphenylene-siloxane [36,37], or 65% phenyl-
89 methylpolysiloxane [38] with thermal degradation and/or band broadening of the highly
90 brominated PBDEs as the main drawback. The target compounds were mainly PBDEs, although
91 sometimes other compound classes such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and polycyclic

92 aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) were included, while the most recent article also includes
93 methoxylated PBDEs and some BFRs [37]. The developed methodologies (based on direct
94 probe, GC and GCxGC) were applied to two electronic waste samples and two samples from car
95 interiors. Nowadays, electronic waste is one of the fastest growing types of waste with a global
96 production of about 50 million tons a year, which has been scarcely investigated yet for flame
97 retardants [39,40]. The fast screening provided by the direct probe could constitute a very useful
98 technique in the recycling of flame retarded polymers under compliance of legislation on the
99 high recycling quotas demanded by the European waste of electric and electronic equipment
100 (WEEE) directive [41]. On the other hand, GC and GCxGC coupled to APCI-HRTOF-MS all
101 provide quantitative results at a low sensitivity or comprehensive information useful for target
102 and untargeted screening, respectively. A total of 30 flame retardants including a variety of tri- to
103 decabrominated diphenyl ethers, new BFRs and PFRs were studied in order to assess the
104 applicability of the new methods for a screening of this type of compounds.

105 **EXPERIMENTAL SECTION**

106 Information about chemicals and suppliers and instrumentation and materials used for sample
107 extraction and analysis are provided in the Supporting Information of this article. The
108 abbreviations for flame retardants and plasticizers recently proposed by Bergman et al. were
109 employed in this article [42].

110 **Optimization of the analysis with direct probe, GC-APCI and GCxGC-APCI-HRTOF-** 111 **MS**

112 The chromatographic separation of flame retardants (including PBDEs and new BFRs
113 analyzed in negative mode) was optimized in different GC capillary columns (specified in

114 Supporting Information). A mix solution containing 24 PBDEs (tri- to decabrominated diphenyl
115 ethers) was tested to assure separations of congeners. For GCxGC (flow modulator)
116 experiments, the flow in the first (0.3-0.8 mL/min) and second (15-55 mL/min) dimensions and
117 the modulation time (2-4 sec) were optimized.

118 Standard solutions of flame retardants (including PBDEs and new BFRs) at a level of 1 mg
119 mL⁻¹ were infused in source and the main MS and source parameters influencing sensitivity
120 (capillary exit and skimmer1, hexapole RF, transfer time, pulse storage time and source
121 temperature) were optimized.

122 **Analysis of flame retardants in e-waste and car interiors samples with direct probe, GC,**
123 **GCxGC /APCI-HRTOF-MS**

124 Four samples, kindly supplied by the Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO,
125 Antwerp, Belgium), two of them coming from printed circuit boards and the other two from car
126 interiors from a recycling park were analyzed by GC and GCxGC-APCI-HR-TOF after solvent
127 extraction and directly without sample preparation with direct probe-APCI-HR-TOF. Samples
128 were supplied as shredder material with particle size < 1 mm.

129 For direct probe analysis no sample preparation was required at all. The glass probe was
130 introduced directly into the shredder material and large particles were removed with a lint-free
131 cotton cloth before introducing it into the MS source. For GC and GCxGC analysis samples were
132 extracted with a mixture of 50:50 v/v acetone:dichloromethane according to a method recently
133 reported for the extraction of plastic baby toys [43]. The extraction process consisted of two
134 consecutive steps of vortexing (1 min) and ultrasonication (15 min) with 5 mL of solvent for
135 aliquots of 200 mg. The samples were left in solvent overnight after the first extraction to assure

136 maximal recoveries. Aliquots of 250 μL were diluted in a ratio 1:3 v/v with toluene and filtered.
137 If necessary, further dilutions (10-250 times) were made to semi-quantify highly concentrated
138 compounds. Internal standards were added at the dilution step (due to the high concentration of
139 the target compounds), acting as injection IS for correction of matrix effects and fluctuations in
140 the signal of the instrument. No destructive clean-up step was applied to prevent losses of
141 analytes. Experiments were made in triplicate. Analytical conditions for analysis are specified in
142 Table 1.

143 Calibration solutions for quantification were made by appropriate dilution of the stock
144 solutions with toluene or methanol for GC and LC, respectively in the range 5-500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ with a
145 concentration of ISs of 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The main ions used for quantification for each target
146 compound are given in Tables S-1 and S-2 and the sum of the main ion (M, as the most intense
147 isotope) plus M+2, M+4 and M-2, M-4 was employed for obtaining maximum sensitivity (see
148 Figure S-1 as an example of the spectra main ion of TBBPA).

149 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

150 **HR-TOF-MS parameters optimization**

151
152 A total of 30 flame retardants and plasticizers were analyzed in negative (the new BFRs ATE,
153 BATE, DPTE, HCDBCO, EHTeBB, TBBPA, α,β,δ ,-HBCD, BEHTBP, BTBPE and tri- to deca-
154 BDE) and positive GC-APCI modes (the PFRs TiBP, TBP, TCEP, TCPP, DOPO, TEHP, EHDP,
155 TEHP, TBOEP, TMPP). Table S-1 and S-2 provide further information about the target
156 compounds. For most BFRs, $[\text{M}-\text{Br}+\text{O}]^-$ was the main ion except for TBBPA and HBCD ($[\text{M}-$
157 $\text{H}]^-$) and BTBPE (fragment $\text{C}_6\text{Br}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}^-$), which is in accordance with recent studies [9-11]. For
158 comparison with direct probe and GC-based methods, the main ions obtained in LC-APCI and

159 LC-APPI sources were also studied. HCDBCO behaved differently in LC-APCI/APPI ($[M+O_2]^-$)
160 than in GC/GCxGC-APCI ($[M-Cl+O]^-$). The mobile phase or carrier gas in this case influenced
161 the ionization (methanol:water for LC and He in GC and GCxGC). For BDE 209, the fragment
162 $C_6Br_5O^-$ was the major ion in LC, while the ion $[M-Br+O]^-$ was predominant in GC due to the
163 higher temperature of the source in LC (285 °C and 200 °C in LC and GC, respectively). The
164 main secondary ions observed in direct probe, GC and GCxGC-APCI-HRTOF-MS were $[M-$
165 $HBr+O_2]^-$, $[M-Br+O_2]^-$ or $[M+O_2]^-$ and were used for confirmation purposes. The main ion of
166 PFRs in APCI positive mode was $[M+H]^+$, except for EHDP ($[M-C_8H_{17}+H_2]$), while secondary
167 ions with enough sensitivity for confirmation purposes were not observed (except for EHDP,
168 $[M+H]^+$). APCI in the negative mode was not sensitive enough for the analysis of the chlorinated
169 PFRs. Flame retardants (name, structure, molecular formula), main and secondary confirmation
170 ion in APCI/HRTOF-MS and retention times in GC and GCxGC are given in Tables S-1 and S-2
171 for negative and positive modes, respectively. The main ion m/z is the most intense isotope and
172 not the theoretical monoisotopic mass due to the complexity of the isotopic distribution of the
173 compounds.

174 The source temperature influenced the sensitivity of PBDEs. Temperatures higher than around
175 250 °C caused extra debromination of PBDEs and a decrease in the intensity of the main primary
176 and secondary ions cited above, with the higher masses less affected. The same behavior was
177 observed for DPTE. For direct probe experiments, higher source temperatures >300 °C caused a
178 faster desorption of flame retardants from the material and an increase in background noise. A
179 slow desorption is preferred to obtain a longer signal in time (several minutes). However, a high
180 temperature (around 400 °C) was employed for removal of residues in the source after each
181 measurement. The source temperature was set at 200 °C for GC and direct probe experiments.

182 This value is lower than that required for LC (285 °C) necessary to reach a compromise between
183 in-source degradation and an efficient mobile phase vaporization/ionization. The MS parameters
184 capillary exit and skimmer 1, hexapole RF, transfer time and pulse storage time had also a strong
185 influence on sensitivity, and were dependent of the m/z value. A compromise was selected as
186 optimal for the mass range of interest m/z 200-1000. (See Tables 1 and S-3).

187 For GCxGC data acquisition, a value of 25 Hz was selected as the minimal acquisition rate to
188 obtain reproducible signals (2-7% RSD for areas and 0.025-0.035% RSD for retention times;
189 peak width in second dimension 300-500 ms). The sensitivity decreased with a factor of 4.5 from
190 5 to 30Hz and with ca. 2.6 from 5 to 20 Hz. After conversion to a *cdf* file format, the size of the
191 file was reduced from ~1 GB to ~350 MB and could be handled by GC Image software. The use
192 of an interpolation tool (nearest neighbour) and an intensity threshold filter (set at 100) both
193 provided by the software was necessary for obtaining clear 2D or 3D plots.

194 **Gas chromatographic separation optimization**

195 For GC and GCxGC a number of columns were tested with the aim of obtaining the widest scope
196 of applicability for flame retardants. The main goal was to reduce the well-known degradation of
197 higher molecular weight PBDEs and to obtain a good separation between the target compounds
198 and matrix components in the case of GCxGC.

199 To obtain a good second dimension separation with GCxGC with a flow modulator, a slow
200 temperature gradient was required in the first dimension. Results for 1st dimension separation
201 experiments are given in Table S-4 and some examples of GC-ECD chromatograms are given in
202 Figure S-2. The trifluoropropyl polysiloxane phase gave better results in terms of peak intensity
203 and width of late eluting PBDEs (especially BDE 209) when compared to BDE 153 and also a

204 better separation of PBDEs and novel flame retardants (taking into account the ratio BDE
205 153/BTBPE as example) and good intensity for the more polar HBCD and TBBPA. The use of
206 fast gradients with high temperature columns did not improve results for the peak intensity and
207 peak width of BDE 209 in this type of columns. The use of ionic liquid columns was not possible
208 due to a strong degradation of compounds with more than five Br atoms.

209 The trifluoropropyl polysiloxane column (Rxi-200) was selected for both GC and GCxGC as
210 first dimension column in further experiments. For GC-HRTOF-MS a faster gradient (ramp of
211 10 °C min⁻¹ to 310 °C) was used to elute all the compounds within about 20 min. Although
212 temperatures higher than the maximum temperature of the GC column program (>10-15 °C) are
213 recommended to prevent peak broadening in the transfer line, the maximum is 300 °C, according
214 to the supplier of the instrument. For this reason, peak broadening was observed for the last
215 eluting compounds (> 8 Br atoms), a behaviour that was not observed when coupling the column
216 to the ECD detector. For overcoming this disadvantage, an empty deactivated silica tube was
217 inserted in the transfer line instead of the column and the flow was increased up to 5 mL min⁻¹ at
218 14 min for eluting the higher PBDEs (peak width of 0.3-0.5 min in the first dimension). The
219 silica tube for the transfer line was replaced within each batch of experiments (around 20
220 injections) to prevent an increase in the width of last eluting peaks, which is possibly due to
221 attached matrix components. A higher temperature in the transfer line temperature would be
222 anyway highly desirable. Figure 1 shows GC-APCI-HRTOF-MS chromatograms of a standard
223 solution (negative and positive mode), an e-waste sample (negative mode) and a car interior
224 sample (positive mode).

225 Regarding the optimisation of GCxGC with a flow modulator, best results were obtained with
226 a medium polar-apolar column combination that because this better prevented the degradation

227 and peak broadening of highly hydrophobic PBDEs and of TBBPA in comparison with the
228 commonly used apolar/medium polar or polar column combination. For example, with the use of
229 wax columns as second dimension, although better second dimension separation was obtained,
230 the peaks were in general very wide (500-1000 ms), even with the use of the recently developed
231 high temperature megaWAX columns (maximum temperature of 300 °C) and PBDEs with more
232 than 6 Br atoms, TBBPA and HBCD could not be analyzed. The final column configuration,
233 Rxi-200/DB-5 was selected as a compromise between the 2nd dimension separation and
234 applicability to a higher number of flame retardants (PBDEs, new flame retardants and PFRs
235 with exception of deca-BDE and HBCD). The length of the DB5 column was set at 5 m (after
236 optimization between 2 and 5 m). Figure S-3 shows the GCxGC-ECD chromatograms of
237 standard solutions of PBDEs and new flame retardants with the Rxi-200 column coupled to
238 megaWAX, ZB-35HT Inferno and DB5 columns as 2nd dimension. Figure 2 (above) shows a
239 GCxGC-APCI(-)-HRTOF-MS chromatogram of an e-waste sample.

240 For comparison purposes standards were also run with LC (for settings see Table S-3). For
241 separation of the HBCD isomers (which is not possible by GC or GCxGC) and the thermolabile
242 higher molecular weight PBDEs, LC-APCI/APPI-HRTOF offers a good alternative at a similar
243 level of sensitivity.

244 **Analytical performance of direct probe, GC and GCxGC APCI-HRTOF-MS for** 245 **analyzing flame retardants**

246 All techniques proposed offer identification of the flame retardants studied with a mass
247 accuracy below 5 ppm (value obtained for the target compounds with internal calibration in each
248 run and from the four samples analyzed with three replicates each in GC, GCxGC and direct

249 probe-APCI-HRTOFMS methods, see Table 3 for concentration). On top of that, the direct probe
250 method offers, an identification within a few minutes, without any sample preparation, a clear
251 advantage over GC methods for a fast screening at high concentration levels. The spectra
252 obtained by direct probe-APCI(-)-HRTOF-MS of an e-waste sample (Figure 2) show the
253 presence of PBDEs (159-1855 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), TBBPA (16232 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) and BTBPE (1689 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$).

254 The second dimension separation introduced by GCxGC provided additional information for
255 screening and better separation from co-eluting interferences and, consequently cleaner spectra.
256 As shown in Figure 2, in the second dimension the target compounds are clearly separated from
257 co-eluting interferences (an example is shown in Figure S-4 for a co-eluting interferent in the 1st
258 dimension that is separated from BDE153 in the 2nd dimension).

259 Direct probe sensitivity is related to the amount of sample and MS noise coming from the
260 matrix. Detection limits (LODs) for screening flame retardants and plasticizers with direct
261 probe-APCI-HRTOF-MS were about 0.025% w/w in samples, which is low enough for technical
262 and recycled materials and below the required level of PBDEs for compliance of legislation of
263 0.1 % w/w [European waste of electric and electronic equipment (WEEE) directive].

264 The sensitivity of GC and GCxGC with APCI in comparison with LC with APPI APCI and
265 ESI sources (already reported in literature with other MS detectors) was compared for a group of
266 flame retardants. Instrumental LODs were calculated from solvent blank determinations fortified
267 at low levels (prepared in triplicate and at concentrations around the expected LODs) by using a
268 signal-to-noise ratio of 3 on the basis of the sum of main ion (M, which does not correspond to
269 the theoretical monoisotopic mass but to the most intense isotope) and M+2, M+4 and M-2, M-4.

270 For GCxGC, the software data analysis 4.0 was used for calculation of LODs taking into account
271 the sum of the modulated peaks for each compound. Results are given in Table 2.

272 As reported before for LC-based methods, APPI and APCI are both suitable sources for the
273 screening of the selected flame retardants, while only TBBPA and HBCD could be also
274 efficiently ionized in the ESI source. When comparing with LC, GC-APCI-HRTOF-MS gave a
275 better range of sensitivity for the flame retardants studied (0.5-25 injected pg) in comparison
276 with LC (1-112 injected pg with APCI source and 2-250 injected pg in APPI source), for which
277 the first eluting compounds (BDE 28, BDE 47, ATE, BATE, DPTE and HCDBCO) showed a
278 significantly lower response (from 2 to 125 times lower). The lower sensitivity of the first eluting
279 compounds in LC could be related to the higher water content in the mobile phase in the first part
280 of the LC program suppressing somehow the ionization process at the relatively low vaporization
281 temperature (285 °C) set to restrict debromination of PBDEs. On the other hand, LC methods
282 showed better sensitivity for octa-, nona- and deca-BDEs, probably due to peak broadening for
283 these last eluting compounds in GC as a consequence of the relatively low temperature of the
284 transfer line. It is worth mentioning that LODs in Table 2 are expressed in absolute amounts
285 (pg) and multiplying factors have been included to calculate LODs in terms of concentration in
286 the samples. The injection volume of the LC method was five times higher. This disadvantage of
287 the GC method could be overcome with large injection volume (LVI) approaches for GC.
288 Anyway, even in concentration terms, the sensitivity would be higher for the GC method for the
289 most polar compounds (e.g. BDE 28, BDE 47, ATE).

290 The LODs in GC-APCI(+)-HRTOF-MS for PFRs were all within the same range and suitable
291 for screening purposes. The calculated values for instrumental LODs were the followings: TiBP

292 (30 pg), TNBP (15 pg) TCEP (2 pg), TCIPP isomers (5-10 pg), DOPO (2 pg), TBOEP (5 pg),
293 EHDP (5 pg), TEHP (10 pg), TPHP (2 pg), TMPP isomers (30-50 pg).

294 Limits of quantification (LOQs) were estimated for GC-APCI-HRTOF-MS taking into
295 account a sample amount of 200 mg and an extract of 10 mL (assuming a theoretical 100%
296 recovery “in a best case scenario”, these values are just indicative since real extraction recoveries
297 were not calculated for samples). Estimated LOQs were in the range of 0.1-4 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$.

298 The recoveries of the internal standards (added after extraction) in the different matrices
299 expressed as mean \pm SD (range) were as follows: 90 \pm 13 (75-115%) for BDE58, 81 \pm 13 (65-104%)
300 for d15-TPHP and 82 \pm 6 (74-90%) for d27-TNBP in GC-APCI-HRTOF-MS. These values show
301 that matrix effects are, even without sample clean-up, were very low, which is a common
302 advantage of GC compared to LC.

303 The precision of the method for quantification was between 2-25% (expressed as relative
304 standard deviation, RSDs, n=6) in GC-APCI-HRTOF-MS for the different compounds mainly
305 due to the heterogeneous nature of the waste samples (even at 1 mm particle size), which
306 consisted of a mixture of very different components. A value of 200 mg was set as sample
307 aliquot to obtain an RSD below a maximum of 25%, suitable for screening purposes.

308 **Sample analysis**

309 Samples were extracted in triplicate and analyzed for screening purposes by direct probe
310 and GCxGC and for quantitative results (RSDs 2-25%) by GC coupled with APCI(+/-)-HRTOF-
311 MS. Retention times, mass accuracy (< 5ppm) and isotopic patterns and a S/N >5 were used for
312 positive identification. Results are shown in Table 3.

313 TBBPA and in to minor extent PBDEs are the main flame retardants present in electronic
314 equipment [44]. A recent article also reports TPHP and TPPO (triphenyl phosphine oxide) as
315 major PFRs in e-waste [45]. Regarding car interiors, PBDEs and some new flame retardants such
316 as DBDPE are the most detected compounds [46, 47].

317 TBBPA was found at a high concentration in one of the printed circuit board samples
318 ($16200 \pm 3000 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ or 1.6 % w/w), which is within the expected concentration in a typical
319 circuit board (1-2% w/w) and at a lower level $71 \pm 15 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ in the other e-waste sample, which
320 contained in general the same flame retardants but at lower levels. Lower levels of TBBPA were
321 found in car interior samples ($7 \pm 1 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ and $15 \pm 2 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). Highly brominated PBDEs (> 6 Br
322 atoms) were found in printed circuit board sample 1 (0.02-0.2% w/w) and printed circuit board
323 sample 2 (0.001-0.01 % w/w). BTBPE was also present in these two samples (0.17-0.004 w/w).
324 Although not included as a target compound, DBDPE (decabromodiphenylethane) was also
325 detected when performing untargeted screening with GC-APCI(-)-HRTOF-MS in e-waste
326 sample 2 (1.6 ± 1 ppm error). The retention time was confirmed by the injection of a standard
327 solution. Both DBDPE and BTBPE are used as substitutes for decaBDE and octaBDE mixtures,
328 respectively.

329 DOPO and EHDP were also detected in printed circuit board samples (<0.01 % w/w). It
330 is worth mentioning that there are not data available about the presence of DOPO in dust samples
331 yet and this is to the best of our knowledge the first time than DOPO is reported in e-waste.
332 DOPO has been proposed as an alternative non-halogenated flame retardant for TBBPA in
333 printed circuit boards since it can also be chemically bound and become part of the epoxy resin
334 backbone, although the higher costs has limited its applicability. TPHP and TMPP were the
335 PFRs at higher levels in printed circuit boards (0.4% and 0.2% w/w in printed circuit board 1 and

336 0.06 and 0.001% w/w in printed circuit board 2, respectively). Samples of car interiors contained
337 mainly PFRs, namely TCIPP (0.04-0.2% w/w) and TPHP (<0.001 % w/w). Levels of PFRs were
338 lower than required for meeting fire protective standards (~ 3% w/w [47]). The mixture of
339 different components in each sample may reflect the more complicated composition of modern
340 flame retardants, often mixtures of BFRs, PFRs and sometimes metal-based flame retardants.

341 In order to check the performance of the technique at lower levels of flame retardants,
342 three dust samples were also analyzed by GC and GC-GC-APCI/HRTOF-MS after a solvent
343 extraction with acetone and toluene and a concentration clean-up with a Na₂SO₄ column (20-80
344 mg sample to a final volume of 500 µL). Lower levels of flame retardants (~50-10.000 ng g⁻¹)
345 were found, mainly PFRs (results are not shown). Finally, despite the suitability of the developed
346 techniques for screening of unknowns, this aspect was not investigated in this study and is the
347 focus of ongoing research in our lab. An example of an unknown peak with an halogenated mass
348 spectra in sample e-waste 1 is shown in Figure S-4.

349 **Conclusions**

350 New analytical methods were developed for flame retardants in e-waste and car interior
351 samples based on direct probe, GC and GCxGC coupled to APCI-HRTOF. Direct probe APCI-
352 HRTOF is a fast (few minutes), easy and inexpensive qualitative screening tool for the
353 identification of flame retardants under compliance of the European WEEE directive. In
354 addition, coupling of GCxGC to a HRTOF by using a soft ionization source was developed for
355 the first time to provide comprehensive information and cluster separation for screening of target
356 compounds and unknowns. As a quantitative technique, GC-APCI-HRTOF-MS generally
357 provides a good sensitivity for a wide range of flame retardants and higher resolution and lower

358 matrix effects than LC-APCI/APPI/ESI-HRTOF-MS. The latter is still required for the
359 separation of HBCD isomers and offers a good alternative for the thermolabile higher molecular
360 weight PBDEs. TBBPA, PBDEs, BTBPE, TPHP, TCIPP and TMPP were found at relatively
361 high concentrations (at $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ to mg g^{-1} levels) in the analyzed samples.

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Figure 1. GC-APCI-HRTOF-MS extracted ions chromatograms of (A) a standard solution of $250 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of IS BDE 58) and (B) e-waste 2 both in APCI negative mode; (C) a standard solution of $250 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of IS TNBPd27 and TPHPd15) except for DOPO ($2000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and (D) car interior 2 both in APCI positive mode

Figure 2. GCxGC-APCI(-)-HRTOF-MS (above) and direct probe-APCI(-)-HRTOF-MS spectra (below) of e-waste 1 sample; (A) full mass range spectra; (B) 450-910 m/z spectra; (C) 250-350 m/z spectra

Table 1. GC, GCxGC and direct probe APCI-HR-TOF-MS parameters

System	Chromatographic separation conditions	¹ TOF parameters
GC-APCI-HRTOF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capillary column <i>Rxi-200</i> (15m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm) GC program negative mode: 1.5 mL min⁻¹ He until 14 min and then up to 5 mL min⁻¹ (100 °C for 3min, to 200 °C at a ramp of 20°C/min and to 310 °C at a ramp of 10°C/min); GC program positive mode: 1 mL min⁻¹ He (100 °C for 3min, to 200 °C at a ramp of 20°C /min and to 225 °C at a ramp of 2°C /min) Injection volume: 1 μL (pulsed splitless), injector temperature 285°C (negative mode) and 250 °C (positive mode) 	Capillary (neg./pos.) -/+1000 V End plate offset (neg.) -1000 (pos.) -500 Corona (neg.) -10000 nA(pos.) +6000 nA Dry gas 2 L min ⁻¹ Nebulizer 4 bar Dry Heater 200 °C Vaporizer temperature 200°C
GCxGC-APCI-HRTOF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First dimension: capillary column <i>Rxi-200</i> (15m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm); second dimension DB5 (5m x 0.25 mm x 0.1 μm) Mobile phase: 0.5 mL/min He in first dimension (100 °C for 3min, to 200 C at a ramp of 15°C/min and to 310°C at a ramp of 2°C/min for positive mode and 3°C/min for negative mode and then hold 25 min) and 50 mL/min He in second dimension (130 °C for 3min, to 205 C at a ramp of 15°C/min and to 315 °C at a ramp of at a ramp of 3°C/min for negative mode and at 2°C/min for negative mode and then hold 25 min) Injection volume: 1 μL (splitless), injector temperature 285°C (negative mode) and 250 (positive mode) GCxGC flow modulator parameters: modulation delay 0.02s, modulation period 4s, sample injection: 3.9 s 	Capillary (neg./pos.) -/+1000 V End plate offset (neg.) -1000 (pos.) -500 Corona (neg.) -10000 nA(pos.) +6000 nA Dry gas 2 L min ⁻¹ Nebulizer 4 bar Dry Heater 200 °C Vaporizer temperature 200 °C
Direct Probe- APCI-HRTOF	-	Capillary (neg./pos.) -/+1000 V End plate offset (neg.) -1000 (pos.) -500 Corona (neg.) -10000 nA(pos.) +6000 nA Dry gas 2 L/min bar Nebulizer 4 bar Dry Heater 200 °C Vaporizer temperature 200 °C

¹TOF detection parameters: capillary exit: ±80 V; Skimmer1: ±26.7 V; Hexapole RF: 250 V (negative mode) and 200 V (positive mode); transfer time: 40; puls storage time: 10; focus on

Table 2. Detection limits (LODs, pg injected) with different sources HRTOF-MS

	LC- APCI	LC- APPI	LC- ESI	GC- APCI	GCxGC- APCI
BDE 28	112	250	-	5	10
BDE 47	22	50	-	1	5
BDE 99	3	5	-	0.5	2
BDE153	3	5	-	0.5	1
BDE183	2	4	-	0.5	5
BDE 203	1	4	-	10	25
BDE 206	1	4	-	10	100
BDE 209	3	3	-	10	-
ATE	94	250	-	25	500
BATE	27	75	-	10	500
DPTE	18	250	-	10	25
HCDBCO	38	250	-	2	10
EHTeBB	4	3	-	0.5	5
BTBPE	5	3	-	0.5	5
BEHTBP	2	2	-	2	10
TBBPA	19	4	20	10	250
α -HBCD	35	25	5		-
β -HBCD	25	10	5	^a 15	-
δ -HBCD	75	25	5		-

^aLODs for HBCD in GC correspond to the sum of isomers (α -, β -, δ -HBCD); injection volume: 1 μ L in GC- and 5 μ L in LC-based methods; for calculation of instrumental LODs in terms of concentration (ng mL⁻¹) multiply by 0.2 in LC methods (according to injection volume) and for calculation of LODs in samples (μ g g⁻¹) multiply values for a factor of 0.15 in GC methods and 0.03 in LC methods

Table 3. Flame retardants and plasticizers concentrations ($\bar{x}\pm SD \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, $n=3$) in waste samples and confirmation by GCxGC and direct probe experiments

	E-WASTE 1			E-WASTE 2			CAR INTERIOR 1			CAR INTERIOR 2		
	Quantification	Screening ^a		Quantification	Screening ^a		Quantification	Screening ^a		Quantification	Screening ^a	
	($\mu\text{g/g}$) GC	GCxGC	DP	($\mu\text{g/g}$) GC	GCxGC	DP	($\mu\text{g/g}$) GC	GCxGC	DP	($\mu\text{g/g}$) GC	GCxGC	DP
ATE	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
BATE	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 28	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
DPTE	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 47	1.5±0.2			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 99	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
HCDBCO	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
EHTeBB	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 153	160±30	+	+	12.9±0.3	+	-	n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 183	1200±260	+	+	80±6	+	-	n.d.			n.d.		
TBBPA	16200±3200	+	+	71±15	+	+	7±1	-		15±2		-
$\alpha,\beta,\delta,-$ HBCD	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
BEHTBP	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 197	290±50	+	+	11±1	+	-	n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 196	390±70	+	+	18±3	+	-	n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 203	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
BTBPE	1700±250	+	+	41±3	+	-	n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 207	850±201	+	+	20±1	-	-	n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 206	40±6	-		10±0.5	-	-	n.d.			n.d.		
BDE 209	1860±200	-	+	71±10	-	-	n.d.			n.d.		
TiBP	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
TBP	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
TCEP	0.8±0.1	-	-	1.5±0.2	-	-	n.d.	-	-	n.d.		
TCPP^b	n.d.			n.d.			200±13	+	+	1640±220	+	+
DOPO	90±20	-	-	35±3	-	-	n.d.			n.d.		
TPHP	3600±460	+	+	590±150	+	+	2.5±0.5	+	-	9±2	+	-
EHDP	10±1	+	-	9±2	+	-	n.d.			n.d.		
TEHP	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
TBOEP	n.d.			n.d.			n.d.			n.d.		
TMPP^b	1800±280	+	+	12±2	+	-	n.d.			n.d.		

^aPresence of flame retardants confirmed by mass ppm error below 5), S/N above 5 and in case of GCxGC also by retention times in first and second dimension with a tolerance RSD level of $\pm 0.1\%$; ^bConcentration calculated on the basis of the individual concentration of the first eluting isomer

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